

Synthesis of Condensed Heterocyclic Systems.

Interaction between 2:5-Dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole and
Some Organic Dihalides.

BY

PRAFULLA CHANDRA RÂY

AND

BIREN CHANDRA GUHA.

It has been shown by Rây, Guha and Das (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1308) that some mercaptans of the heterocyclic series or rather their potassium salts are singularly reactive towards halogenated organic bodies. They have studied the action of the potassium salts of 2-thiol-5-thio-4-pentenyl-4:5-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole and 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole on chloroform, bromoform, iodoform, benzalchloride, monochloroacetic acid, ethylene bromide, etc., and have found that condensation is readily effected in almost all these cases. The dithiol, however, could not be made to condense with chloroform, bromoform and iodoform. They observed that monochloroacetic acid, benzal chloride and ethylene bromide act upon 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole but they were unable to isolate the reaction products in a state of purity as they were found to be insoluble in ordinary solvents.

In view of the comparative scarcity of fused heterocyclic systems of the type which would be expected to be produced by the condensation of 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole with some reactive dihalides like ethylene

dibromide, benzal chloride and thiophosgene, and also in view of the fact that the dithiol has a curious tendency to form "chain compounds of sulphur" (*loc. cit.*), it seemed desirable to make another careful study of these condensations and a systematic attempt to isolate the resulting products.

The condensation of the dipotassium salt of the dithiol with ethylene bromide was more fully studied than those with benzalchloride and thiophosgene. It was found that three distinct types of compounds were formed in this reaction.

(i) One molecule of the dimercaptan condensed with one molecule of ethylene bromide thus giving rise to a new mercaptan, $\text{BrCH}_2\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}\cdot\text{SH}$, though with a poor yield. The presence of a free thiol group was proved by the usual tests. Obviously this is the first step in the reaction and the second and third types of products (*vide infra*) are formed from this intermediate compound.

(ii) One molecule of the dithiol condensed with one molecule of ethylene bromide giving a fused heterocyclic compound, thus;

This compound is produced in the largest yield though it will be noticed that one of the component rings consists of seven members of which three are sulphur atoms. Evidently the presence of sulphur contributes to the stability of the ring system.

(iii) Several molecules of the dimercaptan and ethylene bromide simultaneously took part in the reaction apparently giving rise to a complex brominated compound, having no mercaptanic property, which could not be purified.

The condensation between molecular proportions of the dipotassium salt of the dithiol and thiophosgene produced (1) a crystalline fused heterocyclic compound (II),

(2) a new dimercaptan of the formula $\text{CS}(\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{SH})_2$ and (3) a yellow amorphous compound whose identity could not be established.

The reaction between the dipotassium salt and benzal chloride also gave rise to a fused heterocyclic compound of the formula,

and a dimercaptan of the formula, $\text{CHPh}[\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{SH}_2]$.

The dipotassium salt of the dithiol failed to react with ethylidene chloride even when heated in a sealed tube at 145° . As mentioned above, Rây, Guha and Das noticed that condensation did not take place between 2:5-dithio-1:3:4-thiadiazole on the one hand and chloroform, bromoform and iodoform on the other, while, curiously

enough, the monomercaptan 2-thiol-5-thio-4-phenyl-4:5-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole readily condensed with these. It was suggested therein that probably "the presence of two SK groups in the dimercaptide exercises inhibitory influence on the halogen atoms." In order to test this theory it was attempted to condense both the free ethylene mercaptan and its disodium salt with chloroform by refluxing for 10 hours on the water-bath and by heating in a bomb-furnace at 140° for seven hours but to no purpose. On the other hand it is well-known that sodium ethyl mercaptide readily condenses with chloroform (Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 185; Holmberg, *ibid.*, 1907, 40, 1740) giving orthotrithioformic ethyl ester $\text{CH}(\text{SEt})_3$. Thus the observation that the alkali salts of both the dimercaptans, dithioethylene glycol and 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole, are inert towards chloroform, whereas the alkali monomercaptides of ethyl mercaptan and 2-thiol-5-thio-4-phenyl-4:5-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole readily condense with the same confirms the original suggestion. The above statement, however, does not appear to contain the whole truth. It is to be noticed that both the alkali dimercaptides mentioned above, though inert towards chloroform ethylidene chloride, etc., readily condense with ethylene bromide (V. Meyer, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 3263). This shows that halogen atoms attached to the same carbon are probably less reactive than those that are attached to different carbon atoms. The presence of negative groups will of course render the halogen atoms labile even when they are attached to the same carbon atom. This explains the condensation of 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole with chloropicrin (Ray, Guha, and Das, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1309), and with benzal chloride (*vide supra*) and of ethylene mercaptan with benzal chloride (Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1142).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of the Dipotassium Salt of 2 : 5-Dithiol-1 : 3 : 4-thiadiazole with Ethylene Bromide.—Numerous products are formed in this condensation of which only two have been isolated in a pure state after a great many trials. Five gms. of the dipotassium salt were refluxed directly with a considerable excess of ethylene bromide for about 20 hours. After cooling, the mixture was filtered and washed with a little ethylene bromide. The filtrate (*a*) was reserved for future treatment. The residue (*b*) was washed well with alcohol and then rubbed in a mortar several times with water and then filtered. After complete removal of potassium chloride it was washed with a little alcohol and then very gently boiled with ethylene bromide and filtered hot. The filtrate deposited a bluish white mass which was filtered while still warm and washed repeatedly with alcohol. It was recrystallised from boiling ethylene bromide. It is insoluble in all ordinary solvents but soluble in hot tetrachlorethane. It is insoluble in dil. caustic soda. It shrinks above 115° and melts to a viscous green melt at 132-133°. (Found : S=54.70 ; N=15.96. $C_4H_4N_2S_3$ requires S=54.55 ; N=15.90 per cent. Absence of bromine was proved.) Its insolubility in ordinary solvents makes it probable that it is a polymeric form of the simple molecule but as it decomposes on continued boiling with ethylene bromide its molecular weight determination is not possible. The filtrate (*a*) was evaporated on the water-bath and air was blown over it to volatilise away the ethylene bromide present. It was then washed several times with cold alcohol. The brown viscous liquid which remained was then taken up three or four times with hot alcohol. The alcoholic solution was evaporated to dryness and again extracted with hot alcohol, the

first and the last fractions being rejected. In this manner after repeated extraction a yellow oil was obtained which gave a yellow precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate. This lead salt of the mercaptan was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and dried. (Found: Pb=28.61; N=7.47. $C_8H_8N_4S_6Br_2Pb$ requires Pb=28.79; N=7.78 per cent.).

Condensation of the Dipotassium Salt with Thiophosgene.—Seven gms. of the solid were refluxed in benzene solution with 4.4 c.c. of thiophosgene for 15 hours, the condenser being surmounted by a guard tube containing quick-lime. The reaction product was filtered and washed with a little benzene. The filtrate on the addition of a few drops of alcohol and keeping for some time gradually deposited a yellow precipitate which was filtered off and rejected. The filtrate on standing again for some 3-4 hours deposited beautiful yellow needles which were filtered off. The filtrate again, on the addition of a little alcohol and standing, gave a second and a third crop of crystals which were successively filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness from which by repeated extraction with cold alcohol a new mercaptan was obtained in a tolerably pure state. It was then converted into the lead salt and analysed. (Found: Pb=38.01; N=10.81. $C_8N_4S_6Pb$ requires Pb=37.82; N=10.23 per cent.) The three crops of crystals mentioned above were 4 or 5 times recrystallised from hot absolute alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 110-112°. It crystallised with $1\frac{1}{2}$ molecule of alcohol. On keeping for some days in a sulphuric acid desiccator it lost its crystalline shape and turned into a mobile oil. (Found: S=49.07; C=28.50; H=3.35. $C_8N_2S_6, 1\frac{1}{2}C_2H_5OH$ requires S=49.04; C=27.6; H=3.4 per cent.).

Condensation of the Dipotassium Salt with Benzal Chloride.—Twelve gms. of benzal chloride and 17 gms. of the salt were refluxed in alcoholic solution for 18 hours. Some sulphuretted hydrogen was evolved. The product, after removing benzal chloride by steam distillation, was rubbed in a mortar several times with hot water to remove potassium chloride. The golden yellow solid thus obtained was powdered, taken up several times with hot and cold alcohol and then successively with ether, benzene and acetone, in which it dissolved almost completely. The acetone extract was evaporated to dryness, washed with benzene and then with a little acetone. The residue left behind melted at 195-196°. It is a colourless compound, dissolves completely in cold caustic soda from which it is reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid. Obviously it is a mercaptan. (Found: N=14.55; S=50.15. $C_{11}H_8N_4S_6$ requires N=14.50; S=49.74 per cent.) The benzene extract was evaporated, washed with cold alcohol and again taken up with benzene. The benzene product (m. p. indefinite 85-110°) has the composition of the condensed heterocyclic compound (III). (Found: N=12.07; S=41.88. $C_9H_6N_2S_3$ requires N=11.8; S=40.33 per cent.) The alcoholic extract contains a mercaptan not identified.

Attempted Condensation with Ethylidene Chloride.

The dipotassium salt and an excess of ethylidene chloride were refluxed in alcoholic solution for 10 hours, in benzene solution in a sealed tube on the water-bath, in bomb-furnace without diluent at 140-150° for 6 hours, but to no purpose.